

Emerging Trend of Management in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Enugu State, Southeastern, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the emerging trend of management in small and medium-scale enterprises in Enugu state, South Eastern, Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to: Examine the influence of managerial competency on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Estate State. Assessing the impact of global managerial skill on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu State. A survey of randomly selected Small and medium-scale enterprises in the three most industrially Local Governments (Enugu East, Enugu North and Enugu South) in Enugu State, Southeast Nigeria, was selected for the study. The study makes use of secondary data from the selected small and medium-scale enterprises. The Data were analyzed using Linear Regression Analysis. Pearson Correlation analysis was used as the main statistical tool of analysis. It was supported by descriptive statistics. Pearson Correlation was then used to test the two null hypotheses formulated for the study. linear regression analysis was used to compare the results obtained from the correlation analysis. The results reveal that managerial competency is significantly positive on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise. at 0.848 while the sig-value is 0.001. while global managerial skill is significantly positive on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise. at 0.854 while the sig-value is 0.001. The result is also corroborated by the result of the R2 (0.733) and the Adjusted R2 (0.656) that measure the goodness of the model fitness.

Keywords: Emerging Trend, Management, Small, Medium-Scale, Enterprises, Enugu State, South Eastern, and Nigeria.

1.0 Introduction

With the advent of new technology and leadership paradigms, Small and medium-scale enterprise is undergoing some significant change and evolution all over the world today. Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises is one of the most important segments of socio-economic transformation in any State or Nation. The management of this small and medium scale enterprise and the spirit of adaptation of meeting current trends determine its success. Every year, a new technological approach emerges in small and medium-scale enterprises and it is a big trend to the management system. The management of this important segment of socio-economic transformation (small and medium-scale enterprise) required managerial competency and skills. The managerial competencies in all indications have a positive influence on the performance of Small and Medium-scale Enterprises. The manager's level of education, managerial experience, and knowledge are used to measure the managerial competencies. An emerging trend is a research area that is growing and at the same time attract attention and utility over time in the organization. Knowledge of emerging trends is extremely important to the management of small and medium-scale enterprises and the entire staff who are charged to hold one or two positions. One of those emerging trends in the management of small and medium-scale enterprises is the increasing need for global managerial skills and the growing use of information technology. Nycz, Marian, and Zdzislaw (2015) opine that Globalization is an act that concerns creating economies across the world. The scholars continue to opine that, the global economy is much used in many kinds of technological solutions that make the borders of nations or economic blocks of no significance to be relevant. It helps to remove an existing barrier in the trade and production of goods and services, make the flow of capital and people around the world easier. Effective management of small and medium-scale enterprise contributes significantly to the nation's economy and make the gross domestic product (GDP) to be effectively strong. It helps to reduced unemployment, high level of poverty and generally promotes entrepreneurship activity to empower the economy.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Almost every year, small and medium-scale enterprises experience new changes. These changes can range from small adjustments to internal processes to total overhauls of the small and medium-scale enterprise's products and services, its supply chain, strategy, or structure. The emergence of the covid-19 pandemic has forced many small and medium-scale enterprises to embrace substantial change initiatives in their management. Many small and medium-scale enterprise who managers and staffs lack managerial competency and global managerial skill have been affected negatively by the change.

1.2 Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the emerging trend of management in small and medium-scale enterprises in the Enugu state. The specific objectives are to;

- i. Examine the influence of managerial competency on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Estate State.
- ii. Assessing the impact of global managerial skill on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu State.

1.3 The hypothesis of the study

- i. H_0 : The managerial competence has no positively significant influence on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Estate State.
 H_1 : Managerial competence has a positive significant influence on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Estate State.
- ii. H_0 : The global managerial skill has no positively significant impact on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu State.
 H_1 : The global managerial skill has a positive significant impact on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprises in Enugu State

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise

Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) are the driving force of a nation's economy across the world. SMEs is the skeleton of the economic, it creates an entrepreneurial spirit, it is the major source of workplaces and innovation, its foster competitiveness and employment. Deloitte, (2013) opines that small and medium-scale represent 99.8% of all enterprises, SMEs are the backbone of the service-driven economy.

For some years now, Small and Medium-Scale enterprises have been seen to constitute the foundation upon which all the multinational companies were built. However, small and medium-scale enterprises have been recognized differently by numerous organizations and individuals such that, an enterprise that may be considered small and medium-scale in one envelopment is considered differently in another envelopment. Even within a nation, the classification changes over time, where it is seen big, it might be seen as small. Some common indicators adopted in some of the definitions comprise total assets, the scope of labor adopted, values of yearly turnover, and share of capital investment differs Basil, (2005). The small and medium-scale industries of the Federal Ministry of Industries describe small scale as " an enterprise that has a capital which includes land investment, building, equipment and machinery and working capital of about ₦60,000.00 and having human capital of no more than 50 people" as far back as 1979. The Central Bank's monetary and credit guidelines regarded small and medium-scale enterprises as an establishment whose yearly turnover is less than ₦6,000,000 and capital not exceeding N10,000,000.

Ayaggari et.al (2003) opines that small and medium-scale enterprises definition differs regarding the context, countries, and author". Countries such as Canada, United State of American and Britain describe the terms small and medium-scale as a business that have yearly turnover with certain numbers of paid employees. Britain describes small and medium-scale enterprise as an industry with a yearly turnover of 2,000,000 pounds with the human capital of 200 paid employees Ekpeyong and Nyang, (1992). Subsequently, small and medium scale enterprises are an enterprise with ₦100,000,000 share capital with the human capital of 300 employees in the area of a manufacturing firm. In the area of Wholesale trade, the is ₦300,000,000 share capital with the human capital of 100 employees while the retail trade firm is with ₦100,000,000 shares paid-up capital with the human capital of 50 employees Fatai, (2012). Nevertheless, the monetary policies circular No. 22 of 1988 of Central Bank of Nigeria view small and medium-scale enterprises of the industry as an enterprise with a yearly turnover of no exceeding ₦500,000 (CBN, 2011). The most general and comprehensive definition of SMEs is Ogechukwu (2006) who hint that small and medium-scale enterprises are based on countries with a different point of view. These points of view from different countries are made up of financial strength, numbers of employees, yearly turnover, sales volumes, local operations, owners' autonomy, and managers, relatively small markets compared to their industries and capital which is usually supplied by individual or shareholders, etc. The differences definition and lack of universal definition of SMEs, the European Union in 2003 approved generally accepted definition of small and medium scale enterprises and the micro-business which may be regarded as companies with nothing less than human capital of 250 employees, concerning any financial criteria, a share capital must not exceed €50,000,000 paid-up capital as turnover or €43,000,000 as a balance sheet. Furthermore, the European Union Commission specifies the terms of ownership by stating that small and medium-scale enterprises must be independent with nothing less than twenty-five percent (25%) being owned by outside interest. European Union Commission; (2007).

Managerial Competency.

Managerial competencies have a positive influence on the performance of Small and Medium-scale Enterprises. Managerial experience, education, knowledge, and start-up experience are used to measure managerial competencies Hisrich & Drnovsek, (2002). Management competence is very important in the management of Small and Medium-scale enterprises because it determines their success. Martin & Staines (2008) hint that the main reason why small and medium-scale enterprises fail is the lack of managerial competency. Abdel, Rowena & Robyn (2010) reported that small and medium-scale business owner-managers have a very good financial understanding but lack basic accounting information and it is a serious problem with their financial planning. In the same vein, Alattar, Kouhy & Innes, (2009) opine that in small and medium-scale enterprises, the owner/managers have slight knowledge about financial matters, and those with slight knowledge lack financial planning skills. And they don't regard any information extracted from financial statements.

The Global Managerial Skill

The increasing globalization of the global market has created a need for small and medium-scale managers to acquired global managerial skills. Global managerial skill is the ability to operate in assorted cultural environments

with clear confidence, Longenecker, (2012). In recent time, the more and more small and medium-scale enterprise has chosen to operate in multiple locations across the world. Every manager and employee is highly expected to learn the social customs of other cultures, their language, and their geographical expression. Although it is very expensive to train employees for other social-cultural assignments or foreign assignments and pay them for their new location. The ability to adapt to this new trend is to acquired global managerial skills.

An employee open-minded, who is willing to try new things, flexible, and comfortable in a multicultural setting is the best candidate for global managerial skills, Scarborough et al., (2009).

As the world continues to go around and small and medium-scale enterprises keep expanding alongside, managers will continue to experience more challenges of directing the behavior of employees and meeting more competitors with new technology around the world. Therefore, the small and medium-scale managers must recognize the differences in culture, how the people respond in different ways under the same situations and the burden falls on the boss to produce an expected result while adapting to the differences among the employees in the organization Kolstad, & Wiig, (2015).

Small and medium-scale enterprises can no longer be strictly domestic businesses in the competitive world environment. For businesses across the world, going worldwide is not a preference or a matter of choice, but rather a necessity. Failure to cultivate worldwide markets can be a deadly mistake for modern businesses, no matter the size of the business. To see themselves successful in business, they must go beyond the border in their business's operation. Going worldwide can put a tremendous strain on a small business Scarborough et al., (2009). However, the tendency of going toward convergence has always been developing for some time, the pace has been, creating worldwide business opportunities and competition that never exist even a few years ago. With the astounding rate of economic growth in some countries such as China and India and so on, small and medium-scale enterprise owners would be unwise to ignore any foreign business opportunities, Longenecker, (2012).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Active Learning Model Theory

This theory was propounded by Erickson and Pakes in 1995. The theory is based on the active learning model, which states that an organization used its economic environment actively well and invests to enhance its growth under competitive pressure from both within and outside the organization. The potential and actual growth change over time in reply to the consequences of the organization's investment and those of other performers in the same market. According to this model of learning, managers or owners of Small and Medium-scale enterprises could raise their efficiency through formal education and training that increases their endowments while the government may support their activities through the creation of the enabling environment. Managers or Entrepreneurs of Small and Medium-scale enterprises with higher formal education, work experience, training, and government assistance would therefore be expected to grow faster than those without these qualities. This implies that Small and Medium-scale Enterprises in Nigeria have prospects of experiencing growth and meaningful contributions to employment generation and this can only take place when appropriate investments are made into them by all the stakeholders. This might best be accomplished by government intervention through the provision of financial assistance, capacity building, social infrastructures of Small and Medium-scale Enterprise operators, and convenient taxation policies.

2.2.2 Human Capital Theory (HCT)

This theory was propounded by Schultz in 1993. The theory is anchored on Human Capital Theory (HCT). The Human Capital Theory is emanated from the field of macroeconomic development theory. From the viewpoint of classical economic theory, the human capital (manpower) sees labor as a commodity that can be traded in the relation of buy and sales. The classical theory focuses mainly on the exploitation of labor via capital. Though, unlike the connotation conventionally related to the term labor, human capital refers to the knowledge, skills, and expertise of individuals accumulate via education and training. Strengthening the economic and social import of human capital theory, Becker (2002) opines that, the most valuable of all capital is investments in humans and manpower is the most valuable asset in every organization.

Figure 1: A Model of Human Capital Theory. Source: Swanson and Holton (2001)

In this model, connection 1 is of import to this current study; connection 1 represents the concept of production functions as applied to skills, expertise, experience, and training. The main assumption underlying this connection is that investment in training outcomes in increased skills. Base on the above, it can be observed that human capital in the form of skills and experience contributes to profitability and organizational advantages. The human capital theory (HCT) is a fundamental agent for enhancing organizational performance. Consequently, this current study is anchored on the human capital theory is on the opinion that human capital is a fundamental element in Small and Medium-scale Enterprise performance. The premise is the human capital theory, Armstrong (2006) opines that each individual with their collective skills, experience, and abilities put together to organize for the interest of the organization are now recognized as making an important contribution to performance and organizational success. The theory emphasizes the association between investments in education to improve abilities, skills, and knowledge, and human productive capacity.

2.3 Empirical

Okanazu, O. O. (2018), conduct research on Innovative Strategies Required by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises for Effective Management Operations and National Development in Enugu State. A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions while a t-test was used for testing the null hypotheses. The study reveals that a core business strategy included making the business mobile and digital, improving the distributional systems of the business among others. The result also reveals that an extension of the management of small and medium-scale business strategies to include: rebranding of the business product/services, seeking new advertising methods for the business product/services among others. Similarly, the result reveals that setting outrageous goals to be achieved in business organizations, maintaining sound product value chains in procurement, design, manufacturing, marketing, and distribution, dematerializing of business products, are reinvention strategies required among others. The result of the hypotheses showed no significant difference in the mean ratings of the business operators in the three categories of gender, location, and experience.

Egberi A. K. (2019), researched Determinants of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) Performance in Nigeria: Does Employee Experience and Skills Matter? A cross-sectional research design was employed for the study. The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The result revealed that, employee skills and experience matter for the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. Given the fact that the experience of employees has a significant role to play in Small and Medium-scale Enterprise performance, management should further engage an experienced employee in more coaching and mentoring programs. This can be accomplished by ensuring that inexperienced employees work more frequently under experienced personnel so that they can easily become informed on the operations of the firm as well as to effectively

discharge their job responsibilities. Also, Small and Medium-scale Enterprise management should engage employees in skills acquisition programs to enhance the level of skills of employees in collaboration with the government. Besides, the government at all levels can provide a supporting hand by engaging Small and Medium-scale Enterprises in skills acquisition programs regularly.

Udemba, N. F. (2020), conduct research on Skills Needed for Successful Management of Small and Medium Scale Manufacturing Industries by Entrepreneurs in Anambra State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. The researcher used a structured questionnaire to collect data for the study. Cronbach Alpha was then used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability index obtained was $r = 0.79$. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and t-test. The results showed that analytical and interpersonal skills are highly needed for successful management of small and medium scale manufacturing industries by entrepreneurs in Anambra State. The results also showed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs on the extent analytical and interpersonal skills are needed for successful management of small and medium scale manufacturing industries in Anambra State based on the size of the business.

Meyer D.F. and Meyer N. (2017), researched Management of Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) Development: An Analysis of Stumbling Blocks in A Developing Region. The study adopted a quantitative descriptive cross-sectional research design. Data were analyzed with descriptive frequencies, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Pearson's correlation analysis. Results from the PCA returned five factors. Results then indicated that they are three main stumbling blocks restricting business growth, they are recession and slow growth conditions, weak and volatile exchange rate, and high inflation rates. The correlation results indicated that they are several significant relationships between the various factors. For Small and Medium-scale Enterprise growth, an integrated multiple-sectoral approach is required.

3.0 Methodology

A survey of randomly selected Small and medium-scale enterprises in the three most industrially Local Governments (Enugu East, Enugu North, and Enugu South) in Enugu State, Southeast, Nigeria, was selected for the study. The study sample was drawn from bread bakeries industries, water packaged industries, fashioners industries, and fast-food industries. The selection of the Small and medium-scale enterprises firms was based on the Nigerian National Council of Industry definition that state, small and medium-scale enterprises is a firm with no less than 11-100 employees. But the researchers considered small and medium-scale enterprises with 11- 25 employees. The key instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researchers. The instrument was designed in four Likert scale formats, with responses ranging from Agree, Strongly Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. A test-retest method was used to establish good reliability for the research instrument. Small and medium-scale enterprise performance was measured through the firm's objective. Employee's performance was measure base on the firm turnover such as return on investment of the firms. The study makes use of secondary data from selected small and medium-scale enterprises. The Data were analyzed using Linear Regression Analysis, SPSS vision 21.

Model Specification

The influence of managerial competency and global managerial skill was used as the independent variables while the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise is the dependent variable for the study.

Using Y and X as an expression for the variables.

$$Y = f(X)$$

Y= Dependent Variable

X= Independent Variable

Where

Y = performance of small and medium-scale enterprise

X = Influence of managerial competency and global managerial skill

$$Y = (y_1)$$

$$X = (x_1, x_2)$$

$$Y=f(X)$$

$$y= f(x_1) \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 1}$$

$$y= f(x_2) \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 2}$$

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_1x_1+ \beta_2x_2 + e\dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 3}$$

Therefore;

$$PRN = \beta_0+ (\beta_1ET + \beta_2EO) + \epsilon$$

Where:

PSMEs= Performance of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprise

IMC= Influence of managerial competency

GMS= Global managerial skill

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

The study was conducted to examine the emerging trend of management in small and medium-scale enterprises in Enugu state, South Eastern, Nigeria. Secondary data was used and it was obtained from the selected small and medium-scale enterprises.

Table 4.1 present the data.

YEAR	PERFORMANCE	MANAGERIAL	GLOBAL
	OF SMEs	COMPETENCY	MANAGERIAL
	(KOBO)	NGN (000)	SKILL
			NGN (000)
2019	61.50	266	131
2018	44.50	244	121
2017	10.00	181	72
2016	29.00	151	50
2015	27.50	143	45
2014	25.50	133	43
2013	20.00	116	36
2012	12.55	97	32
2011	12.55	80	25
2010	12.55	65	23

Source: research field survey

4.2 Data Analysis

The secondary data collected for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics, linear regression, and correlation analysis and the results presented.

Table 4.2.1

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Performance of SMEs	25.5650	16.48843	10
Managerial competence	147.6000	66.35293	10
Managerial skill	57.8000	38.62296	10

Table 4.2.1 presents the descriptive statistics describing the characteristics of the variables used in the study. The descriptive statistics include measures of central tendency, which are the mean and median, and measures of dispersions which include standard deviation. The results show the mean of the variables are: Performance of SMEs= 25.5850, PRN= 147.6000 and LES= 57.8000 and standard deviation, Performance of SMEs= 16.48843, PRN= 66.35293 and LES= 38.62296 etc.

Table 4.2.2

Variables Entered/Removed			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Managerial Competency Global Managerial Skill		Enter

- a. Dependent Variable: performance of SMEs
- b. All requested variables entered.

Table 4.2.3

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.856 ^a	.733	.656	9.66652	.733	9.593	2	7	.010

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Managerial Competency Global Managerial Skill
- b. Dependent Variable: performance of SMEs

Table 4.2.4

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1792.724	2	896.362	9.593	.010 ^b
	Residual	654.091	7	93.442		
	Total	2446.815	9			

- a. Dependent Variable: performance of SMEs

b. Predictors: (Constant), Managerial Competency Global Managerial Skill

Table 4.2.5

Model		Coefficients			T	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.645	13.170		.049	.962
	Managerial Competency	.076	.235	.308	.325	.755
	Global Managerial Skill	.236	.404	.552	.583	.578

a. Dependent Variable: performance of SMEs

Table 4.2.6

Residuals Statistics					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	11.0402	51.8844	25.5650	14.11352	10
Residual	-21.46848	9.61562	.00000	8.52507	10
Std. Predicted Value	-1.029	1.865	.000	1.000	10
Std. Residual	-2.221	.995	.000	.882	10

a. Dependent Variable: performance of SMEs

Table 4.2.7

		performance of SMEs	Managerial Competency	Global Managerial Skill
Pearson Correlation	performance of SMEs	1.000	.848	.854
	Managerial Competency	.848	1.000	.978
	Global Managerial Skill	.854	.978	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	performance of SMEs	.	.001	.001
	Managerial Competency	.001	.	.000
	Global Managerial Skill	.001	.000	.
N	performance of SMEs	10	10	10
	Managerial Competency	10	10	10
	Global Managerial Skill	10	10	10

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Source: SPSS vision 21

Test of Hypotheses

The test of hypothesis Presented in table 4.2.7 is the correlation analysis of the variables. The correlation results were used to test the two null hypotheses formulated for the study. In deciding on the hypotheses, the following steps were taken:

- i. The hypotheses were restated in null and alternate forms
- ii. The decision criterion or criteria were stated
- iii. The presentation of the correlation result
- iv. The null hypothesis is rejected or accepted based on the decision criterion or criteria.

Test of Hypothesis One

Step One: Restatement of hypothesis in a null and alternate form

H₀: The managerial competence has no positively significant influence on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Estate State.

H₁: Managerial competence has a positive significant influence on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Estate State.

Step Two: Decision Rule/Criteria: Reject H₀ if Sig-Value is less than 0.05, otherwise accept H₀.

Table 4.2.7 presents the result of the correlation analysis used to test the hypothesis formulated for the study. From the table, the correlation coefficient of managerial competency (MC) is positive 0.848 while the sig-value is 0.001. Therefore, managerial competency is significant at 0.05, level of significance is (0.001 < 0.05). Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative that state, managerial competency has a significantly positive influence on the success of small and medium scale enterprises in southeast Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Step One: Restatement of hypothesis in a null and alternate form

H₀: The global managerial skill has no positively significant impact on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu State.

H₁: The global managerial skill has a positive significant impact on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu State.

Step Two: Decision Rule/Criteria: Reject H₀ if Sig-Value is less than 0.05, otherwise accept H₀.

Table 4.2.7 presents the result of the correlation analysis used to test the hypothesis formulated for the study. From the table, the correlation coefficient of global managerial skill (GMS) is positive 0.854 while the sig-value is 0.001. Therefore, global managerial skill is significant at a 0.05 level of significance (0.001 < 0.05). Based on this, we reject the null hypothesis that global managerial skill does not have a significantly positive impact on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in southeast Nigeria. Therefore, we accept global managerial skills have a significantly positive impact on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in southeast Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

Discussion of Hypothesis One

The test of hypothesis one reveals that the null hypothesis was rejected. The result, thus, shows that managerial competence is significantly positive on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise and it has a strong significantly positive influence on the success. The result was corroborated by the result of the R² (0.733) and the Adjust R² (0.656) that measure the goodness of the model fitness in table 4.2.3. From the regression result in the table, the regression coefficient of a good road network is 0.076 while the significant value is 0.755. Thus, in both

the correlation and regression results, managerial competence is positive and significantly related to the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Southeast Nigeria.

Discussion of Hypothesis Two

The test of hypothesis two indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected. The result shows that global managerial skill is significantly positive on the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise and it has a strong significantly positive impact on the performance. The result was corroborated by the result of the R^2 (0.733) and the Adjusted R^2 (0.656) that measure the goodness of the model fitness in table 4.2.3. From the regression result in the table, the regression coefficient of global managerial skill is positive at 0.236 while the significant value is 0.578. This implies that global managerial skill contributes to the performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu state, Southeast, Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, we conclude that, managerial competence significantly positive influence on the success of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu state. and global managerial skills have a great significant impact on the rapid performance of the small and medium-scale enterprise in Enugu state, Southeast Nigeria.

5.1 Recommendation

Base on the finding, we hereby recommence that, the owners or managers of the small and medium-scale enterprise should enable to;

- i. Improve in their managerial competence since it directly influences the management of the small and medium-scale enterprise to increase their success.
- ii. They should haired expertise into their respective field so their employees can work under them to acquire more global managerial skills since it directly improves their performance.

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